

FACTORS NEGATIVELY INFLUENCING THE ACTIVITIES OF OPERATIONAL SUBDIVISIONS OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IN COMBATING FRAUD

Ashurov Otabek Ummatillaevich

Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of
Uzbekistan Instructor of the Department of Operational Search
Activities, Major

E-mail: Ashurovotabekk990@gmail.com

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Abstract: The article presents factors negatively influencing the activities of operational units of internal affairs bodies in combating fraud, their types, current state, and specific features of improving these activities. It provides a number of proposals for eliminating problems and shortcomings related to this work. The article develops proposals and recommendations for improving anti-fraud activities, taking into account the best practices of foreign countries in eliminating factors that negatively affect these efforts, as well as similarities and differences from our national legislation and the aspects mentioned above.

Proposals for practical implementation of these recommendations are also provided.

Keywords: Operational units of internal affairs bodies, fraud, factors negatively affecting anti-fraud activities, criminal law reforms, experience of foreign countries, legal basis for combating fraud, legislative acts, ensuring citizens' rights and freedoms, socio-political rights.

Entrance

Recently, in our country, we have witnessed an increase in the commission of fraudulent crimes, including the misappropriation of property and rights to it by criminals, especially fraudsters. Looking back at history, it is regrettable that despite our ancestors considering religion, morality, honor, and honesty as their highest goals, the number of current descendants of the Uzbek people committing various crimes, including fraud, is increasing[1]. In our sacred religion of Islam, misappropriation of others' property through deception, fraud, and making false promises is strictly forbidden. It is advisable to pay great attention to advocacy and awareness-raising work among the population on combating fraud and modern forms of fraud, analyzing the problems in legal relations that are occurring in the lives of our compatriots today, and working accordingly precisely and purposefully[2]. In this regard, we consider it necessary to improve the organizational and tactical foundations of combating fraud when improving the comprehensive training of employees of operational units of internal affairs bodies, whose main service tasks are ensuring the protection of human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, the property of legal entities and individuals, the security of the individual, society, and the state, the prevention, detection, suppression, and exposure of crimes, as well as the identification and discovery of persons involved in the preparation and commission of crimes.

Relevance: Due to the increase in fraud crimes in our country in recent years, a special place is occupied by improving the service activities of employees of operational units of internal affairs bodies in order to understand the organizational and tactical foundations of combating these types of crimes and their specifics[4]. In particular, special attention is paid at the state level to reforming the activities of operational units of internal affairs bodies.

Statement of the problem: As a result of the reforms being implemented in the system of operational units of internal affairs bodies, the organizational structure of operational units is being reformed. In particular, the concept and prospects for improving the organizational and tactical foundations and specific aspects of combating fraud, the specific distribution of efforts to combat fraud, the preservation of peace and public order among citizens, the essence and content of their functions and tasks have been revised, and fundamentally new mechanisms for maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens have been created in the country, and norms have been introduced into the legislation regarding the strict observance and fulfillment by bodies carrying out operational-search activities and their employees of the requirements of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this Law, and other legislative acts.

In this article, based on the requirements of the norms of our newly adopted Constitution regarding ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens, their peaceful life and guarantees of their security, we will examine the issue of administrative and legal reforms being implemented in the system of internal affairs bodies and analyze legal documents aimed at improving their activities[6].

The purpose of the research is to conduct a scientific analysis of the activities of operational units of internal affairs bodies in combating fraud, the specifics of the organizational and tactical foundations of fraud, the content and essence of the reforms being carried out in this area, to assess the results of their implementation, to study important issues related to the content and practical implementation of the tasks set, as well as the organizational and legal aspects of this activity.

and tactical foundations.

Research methods: Operational units of internal affairs bodies

Scientific analysis of the content and essence of criminal-legal reforms, assessment of their implementation results, study of important issues related to the content, essence, and practical implementation of assigned tasks, development of proposals and recommendations for improving the organizational and tactical foundations of fraud, prospects for improving its organizational and tactical aspects, and improving the organizational and legal framework of this activity.

Today, new types of fraud are emerging. Including submitting proposals for doing business through the Internet information system, obtaining a plastic card number under various pretexts

and withdrawing funds from them, obtaining funds by deceiving by promising to send them abroad for work, leasing cars, enrolling them in studies abroad, and transferring their studies[7].

One of the main reasons for the increase in such crimes is the desire of victims to satisfy their needs faster, bypassing established rules, a strong desire for quick enrichment, and the use of mass media.

and overconfidence in online ads.

The high frequency of repeat offenses in this crime can be characterized by the fact that in many cases, persons who have committed fraud are not afraid of punishment due to the application of institutions of exemption from liability and punishment. Due to the fact that in judicial and investigative practice there are cases where one person has been convicted of fraud 8-10 times, and there are cases where fraud continues even during investigative and

judicial proceedings for previous acts, we consider it necessary to make several amendments to the legislation[8].

Analysis of the causes of crimes in the activities of operational officers of operational units of internal affairs bodies in combating fraud, as well as the practice of combating crime, shows that in many cases, the perpetrator of fraud primarily pursues the goal of acquiring material and property assets[9]. It is known that this selfish goal indicates not only the satisfaction of one's own property needs, but also the presence of other necessary goals in the individual.

When analyzing the factors hindering and negatively affecting the work of operational units in combating fraud, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Firstly: the necessity of noting that the crime of fraud, by its content and essence, is separately related to the socio-economic situation in society, the psychological and social status of the individual, the upbringing received in the family, or the working environment;

Secondly: the state of corruption and unemployment in the country also play a special role in determining the causes and conditions of fraud crimes;

Thirdly, the victim's role, behavior, and level of legal awareness are of particular importance in preventing fraud. Therefore, the main reason for falling into the trap of "persons who are the most experienced in this field and quickly resolve cases" in fraud crimes is, first of all, the lack of sufficient knowledge of the victims about fraud crimes and the persons committing them. In our opinion, in order to increase the legal knowledge of the population and prevent easy falling into the trap of fraudsters, as well as in order to awaken respect for the law among the population, especially among citizens with difficult upbringing, it is necessary to systematically organize open dialogues with the population in mahallas in cooperation with the courts and expand the scope of conducting field court sessions in criminal cases in the field of fraud;

Fifthly: it is necessary to monitor LLCs and citizens receiving material assets from citizens with the condition of returning them 2-3 times after a certain period, to inspect their bank accounts, and, if necessary, to take measures to freeze them;

Sixthly: it is necessary to constantly monitor the banking operations of persons who have previously committed fraud crimes and those who were in close contact with them;

Seventhly: the socialization of persons convicted of committing fraud should be carried out in cooperation with the seven working in mahallas;

Eighth: It is necessary to develop a register of persons who have committed fraud, to publish their lists monthly online, to prevent persons who have committed fraud from re-occupying authorized positions, to prevent them from committing repeated crimes, and to ensure their transition to the path of correction in cooperation with the public[11].

A swindler's personality is such that they can convince anyone. One of the primary features on the path to acquiring material resources is the ability to convince oneself, for which they often have sufficient knowledge in the field, the latest information. This person assures you that you will receive a large sum of money or some profit as a result of this. Whether we like it or not, everyone is interested in easy money or easy ways to achieve something. Because they know this subtle point well, they know how to act. They take the money from your hands, sell it for a month, and promise to turn your 50 million soums into 80 million soums. One of the most widespread types of fraud, we've seen people deceiving several naive people under the guise of getting a car. In our experience, there have been

scammers who fraudulently obtained funds from dozens of citizens by concluding contracts with the condition of obtaining houses in the Sergeli district, which are being built on preferential terms in the city of Tashkent. There are many scammers who promise to get you into university. Among the victims, one can often find people with higher education and a certain position in the life of society and the state. What does this mean? These fraudsters are not just ordinary people, but individuals who can select citizens from any society's life as their prey and convince them. During court proceedings, if necessary, they try to deceive the court. Upon hearing the fraudster's words, law enforcement officers and judges may conclude that this is not a fraudster and that he lost the money for objective reasons. Know that if they say that they can resolve social relations easily, easily, and pleasantly, the law is certainly being circumvented, and you should consider this situation as an attempt to seize your material assets," says the experienced legal representative.

In this regard, we considered it our duty to warn citizens. If someone offers to buy you a house cheaper than the stated price, offers a lease agreement on dubious terms, or says they know different ways to send them to study or work abroad, think carefully before immediately giving them the money. Any person might be eyeing the valuables in your hands. Our message to fraudsters is that punishment before the law is inevitable for any fraudulent actions you commit[12].

Based on the foregoing, it should be noted that the increase in modern forms of fraud requires the improvement of the legislative framework for combating this crime, the analysis of the effectiveness of imposed punitive measures, and the revision of the institutions of sentencing, release from liability, and punishment.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that today one of the most pressing issues is the identification of negative situations arising in the activities of operational units in the fight against fraud, taking necessary decisions to prevent, combat and eliminate them, participating in the development of draft normative legal acts on combating fraud, identifying and combating fraudulent crimes that threaten the interests of state bodies and the people, conducting pre-investigation checks and preliminary investigations of fraudulent crimes, carrying out operational-search activities, identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions that contribute to the commission of fraudulent crimes that threaten the rights and freedoms of citizens. After all, the safety and peace of every citizen in our country are of great importance to our state[13].

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